

Present and Future of Arts-Based Peacebuilding

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGY

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This paper presents a revised and condensed version of our 2023 research on arts-based peacebuilding within the field of social psychology.

ABSTRAT

The Arts-Based Peacebuilding field is growing rapidly with multidirectional approaches. This work analyzes it with a decolonizing and glocal perspective, adding an aesthetic framework of art as a mediator for peacebuilding and clarifying methodologies in art use and data collection inclusively. It highlights the effectiveness of artistic interventions in transforming psychosocial conflicts and building communities while noting the need for systematic, longitudinal approaches to capture long-term impacts, involving various community strata, including audiences and indirect participants. A mix of qualitative and quantitative research, as in psychology, will identify trends and patterns. The work proposes unifying "arts-based" and "peacebuilding" into a single comprehensive term to facilitate knowledge exchange, strengthening methodology, and providing a stable framework for researchers and glocal communities. It suggests a mixed-method approach including various arts and peacebuilding subcategories like "Conflict Resolution, Transformation", "Reconciliation," "Community Building," and "Social Cohesion" to encompass 45,296 studies for significant advancement.

Keywords: peacebuilding, arts-based, conflict, community, peace.

ABSTRAT	2
Keywords:.....	2
1. INTRODUCTION	4
1.2 A Theoretical Framework for Arts, Aesthetics, and Social Transformation.	5
1.3 Building up on Arts-Based Concept	7
1.4 Art as a Catalyst for Social Change	9
1.5. The Ambiguity of Peacebuilding Concept: Challenges and Implications	10
1.6. Art in a decolonized peacebuilding strategy	10
1.7. Justification of the Research.....	12
1.8. Objectives	14
2. METHODOLOGY	14
2.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria	15
2.2 Sample Selection Procedure and Flow Diagram	15
3. RESULTS.....	16
3.1. Results Analysis	25
4. CONCLUSION.....	27
4.1. Improvements for the future	28
4.2. Limitations of this research.....	30
5. BIBLIOGRAPHY	31

1. INTRODUCTION

"Truth is a pathless land..."

Jiddu Krishnamurti

Arts, whether classical or popular such as music, theater, dance, painting, poetry, and sculpture among others, are deeply rooted in cultures all over the globe, with evidence of their existence dating back 40,000 years to the Paleolithic era and having never disappeared in the arc of history since then (Both, 2009). They move within and beyond their geographical, social and historical context, promoting communication, dialogue, debate and complementing dialectics. The consolidation of lasting peace demands more than a cognitive and rational intervention in a political and legal treaty, more than pure logic. In the conflict contexts that disturb our contemporary world, violence often infiltrates the minds and bodies, as well as the spirit of individuals, both in children and adults. These conflicts are not susceptible to transformation exclusively through rational processes, expression approaches are needed that integrate the paradox and enable the articulation of thoughts and emotions that escape conventional language (Brandeis University, 2023). The production of the arts is dynamic, continues to be created influenced by personal and collective events, and its expression is spread beyond the limit of the psychosocial context where a work was born. In the past, this process of creation and cultural exchange of the arts between individuals, collectives, or societies was transmitted through trade routes, migrations, the results of wars, the spread of religious doctrines, and through diplomacy, but now, especially with globalization and the spread of the internet, this phenomenon can occur anywhere in the world without the processes described. The arts have the advantage of being able to overcome linguistic and cultural barriers, although it is necessary to bear in mind that their different dimensions are driving forces capable of provoking different emotions, thoughts, and feelings depending on the theme they address, as well as a specific perceptual impact on each individual, conditioned by the psycho-physical state, different according to the subject who perceives it and the conditions of the cultural, geographical and emotional context of the moment. Their potential as agents of societal transformation allows them to be seen as effective tools for resolving community or large group conflicts by visualizing a peaceful future. Their importance as mechanisms of social change lies in their natural creation and diffusion within communities. However, the success of their use in peace consolidation can be jeopardized when manipulated for political motives, making the art appear artificial and less effective. This research will focus on arts-based practices and peacebuilding.

1.2 A Theoretical Framework for Arts, Aesthetics, and Social Transformation

Throughout history, many have tried to define art, but no thinker has succeeded in creating a stable, universally accepted theory. Art, existing since the dawn of humanity, remains ineffable—both its power and its limit. This section aims not to define art, but to understand its roots, attributes, and its sometimes conflicting relationship with logic, positivism, and science. We will explore its essence to develop a framework for "arts-based peacebuilding" (ABP) that is functional both locally and globally.

Philosophically, Kant's "Critique of Judgment" (1790) distinguishes between the objective logic of pure knowledge and the subjective aesthetic quality of art. The aesthetic quality relates to the subject's experience, not the object itself, and involves pleasure or disgust associated with the representation. This framework will help understand the role of art in peacebuilding efforts.

In his last book, "The Eye and the Spirit" (1964), Merleau-Ponty challenges science, claiming it manipulates things without truly inhabiting them. He argues that art feeds on raw sense, which positivism ignores, and manifests invisible content. Psychology mediates between pure science and the humanities, focusing on qualitative aspects of human experience like beliefs, emotions, values, cultural norms, and personal interpretations of the world.

To explain, Merleau-Ponty (p. 21) invites us to explore the 17,500-year-old animal paintings in the Lascaux cave in France. These paintings do not exist in the same way as the physical cracks and bulges of the limestone; they skillfully adhere to the wall, radiating without releasing their elusive hold. The paintings are not seen as objects but engage the observer's imagination. One sees according to the painting or with it, creating a dynamic interaction. Art allows artists to express their perception of the world, and viewers participate in this expression through their interaction with the artwork.

Art is continuously in dialogue between artists, artworks, and viewers within a specific context. Each contributes to the evolving meaning of the artworks in an uncontrollable community relationship. This interaction is vital for conflict transformation, stimulating ongoing debate and encouraging both personal and community dialogue. However, this unpredictability also highlights art's scientific limitations, as it cannot be fully controlled.

According to Danto (2014), each work of art materializes a meaning, turning the works into meanings that take shape. Danto explores the question of what distinguishes a work of art from an ordinary object, arguing that this distinction lies in the interpretation of the work within the "art world", and the context of the art world, is where a work is perceived and analyzed internally, since it has a meaning and

interpretation that transcends its physical appearance and is made by the community, either locally or globally, which engages in a dialogue about the artwork and the meaning of it for them.

In the aesthetics lessons titled "Poetics and Rhetoric" given by Professor Elio Franzini at the University of Milan in 2007, the relationship between aesthetics and rhetoric is clearly established. Rhetoric is considered the mother of aesthetics, providing the method for the art of speaking. The origin of rhetoric dates back to Syracuse in 465 BC, where Empedocles taught citizens to assert their rights in court, implicitly acting as a mediator in conflict resolution. This process was born from the need to defend property rights over cultivated lands, seen as a means of achieving freedom from tyrants. Empedocles's approach was based on a bottom-up model, where power was given to citizens to express and defend their rights. Can we consider Empedocles the first formal mediator for peacebuilding? (Franzini, 2007).

Aesthetics, emerging from the roots of rhetoric, seeks to establish its own distinct status, whether "scientific" or cognitive. Theories of the arts rely on the foundational work of rhetoric, which institutionalized the relationship between "ethos" (affective and moral order) and "pathos" (purely affective order). Cicero further developed rhetoric with the concepts of "docere" (to teach), "delectare" (to delight), and "movere" (to move), emphasizing originality and creativity beyond the constraints of rhetorical limitations. In modern culture, from Descartes to Hume and beyond, there is a persistent notion of two distinct cultures: one that seeks truth through demonstrative knowledge and clarity, and another that navigates the emotional and often perceived as ambiguous world of artistic expression. This divide is evident in our research, which strives for clear and precise conclusions while recognizing the importance of emotional and subjective experiences. Artistic languages subtly influence cognitive judgments, operating almost imperceptibly within the rigorous framework of logical thinking. It is in this delicate interplay that the power of art becomes apparent (Franzini, 2004).

In modern culture, from Descartes to Hume and beyond, there exists a notion of two distinct cultures: one pursuing truth through demonstrative knowledge and clarity, and another navigating the emotional and ambiguous world of artistic expression. Our research reflects this divide, aiming for clear conclusions while acknowledging the importance of emotional and subjective experiences. Artistic languages subtly influence cognitive judgments, operating within the framework of logical thinking, revealing the power of art (164-5).

Aesthetics, distinct from logic, suspends judgment and explores non-formalizable horizons linked to sensory metaphors. Art performs multiple roles: social, cultural, theoretical, and educational (docere), conveying experiences instantly, such as church paintings for rural audiences. Art also aims to move emotionally (movere) and provide aesthetic pleasure (delectare). Rhetoric provides a framework for art to teach, move, and delight, building a community based on shared feelings. Representation gains value through emotional interpretation, which can be discussed and argued, but not demonstrated (pp. 165-172).

Blaise Patrix, creator of "art socia(B)le" (Patrix, 2022), who has worked in various parts of the world to make collective mural painting and circle painting with about 10,000 people over the last 30 years and has used his art as a form of research, as well as a method, synthesizes the value of painting in this case as serving for mediation:

"Art cultivates signs of recognition. The phenomenon of recognition in all its aspects, openness to the unknown, identification, gratification, and gratitude, is par excellence the guarantor of a respectful and dignified relationship. Recognition of oneself, of the other, by the other, promotes the flourishing of "becoming together".

- Recognition is shared beyond differences: two enemies can appreciate the same work.
- Art expresses what cannot be explained.

1.3 Building up on Arts-Based Concept

In the academic sphere, the arts, despite their conceptual complexity, are characterized by fundamental attributes recognized across cultures. One key attribute is the artistic object, which can be a physical entity, experience, or idea, valued for its intrinsic worth rather than functional utility. Another is the imaginative experience for both creators and viewers, serving to explore ideas and emotions. Art production requires specialized skills, a cultural reference, and an art world that reflects mastery and competence in the chosen medium (Fancourt and Finn, 2019).

Pioneers in arts-based educational research (ABER) Barone and Eisner (1997) observe that ABER allows ambiguity and liberates the researcher to use aesthetic forms and expressive language, they identify the term as an umbrella for all literature on arts-based methods, although it has not been used as such by subsequent authors and has been simplified to arts-based research (ARB) to include other fields, not just education.

As analyzed in the scoping review by Coemans and Hannes (2017), ABER have been used both as data collection techniques and as diffusion techniques. In the first case, art forms are considered research data themselves. Images and sculptures replace traditional interview transcripts and observation data, supporting the researcher's interpretation process. This way, art allows research participants to communicate their situations, experiences, concerns, and daily challenges to the researchers. In other cases, art is used as a medium to translate and disseminate research findings through dramatic representations, dances, painting exhibitions, visual representations, songs, and artifacts. Often found in qualitative investigations, these methods question the predominance of pure science and rationality. The authors note this as part of the emergence of the postmodern period, which embraces a more pluralistic attitude towards research. However, as discussed earlier, the origin of this issue is much older.

In the Oxford Handbook of Qualitative Research (2014), Chilton and Leavy highlight that ABR supports the arts' inherent capabilities of opposition, subversion, transformation, and resistance. They argue that ABR resists dominant paradigms and authorities, generating fresh energy and innovative ideas through human creativity. ABR produces data beyond typical qualitative research methods like interviews or

participant observation, fostering greater engagement among participants and the research audience.

In their transdisciplinary research based on a literature review, Wang et al. (2017) classify ABR into three main categories (Table 1):

a) **Research on Art:** This category investigates issues related to art without creating an artistic form or material reality. It aims to understand the process of artistic creation itself.

b) **Art as Research:** This involves artist-researchers seeking a deeper understanding of art and artistic creation through their work.

c) **Art in Research:** Here, art is actively used by artist/researcher participants as a creative process in one or more stages of a research project, particularly in the study of social and behavioral sciences. (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison between research about art, art as research and art in research

Families	Research about art	Art as research	Art in research
Nature	Both qualitative and quantitative inquiry	Artistic inquiry	Qualitative inquiry
Primary identity of the artist-researcher	Researcher	Artist	Researcher
The role of art	Art as a content area	Art as a way of inquiry	Art as a methodology or a means to an end
The relationship between art and research	Qualitative (or quantitative) inquiry into artistic topics	Research methods supporting artistic inquiry	Artistic forms supporting qualitative inquiry
Perspective of the artist-researcher	Outsider	Insider	Insider

Note: adapted from Wang et al. (2017)

Currently, **there is not general classification framework for all art-based research.** However, Wang et al. (2017) provide a classification using five categories: visual art, sound art, literary art, performing art, and new media, each with its own subcategories in which the author build up for a broader classification, sculpture and ceramics as three-dimensional art, and storytelling as performing art. This provides a good starting point for a more comprehensive classification which needs to be open in order to include new methods.

Table 2

Classification of art forms with dimension and categories.

ART FORM	DIMENSION	CATEGORIES
Visual Art	Two-Dimensional	Painting, Drawing, Photography, Comics, Collage, Graphic Novels
	Three-Dimensional	Objects in Space, Creative Recycling, Ceramic, Sculptures
	Time-Based	Movies, Documentary, Animation, Video
Sound Art	Time & Space	Radio, Sound Environments
Literary Art	Time-based	Poetry, Fiction, Graphic Novels, Short Story, Drama used within Script
Performative Art	Multidimensional	Theater, Dance, Music, Stage Poetry, Storytelling
New Media	Time-Based	Video Games, Blogs
Multidisciplinary		Varius

Note: Classification of art formas used in the arts based research with reframing and adding from the author (Wang *et al*, 2017)

1.4 Art as a Catalyst for Social Change

Rathje et al. (2021) demonstrated that watching live theater can increase empathy and charitable behavior, measured through participant donations. The study, involving 2 theater companies, 3 plays, and 1622 participants, showed that fictional narratives can alter socio-political beliefs and behaviors. They identified two mechanisms: Narrative Transport Theory, where immersion in a story changes attitudes, and the persuasive power of narratives that evoke psychological transport—a blend of attention, imagination, and emotion.

Tumanyan and Huuki (2020) reviewed 20 studies (1997-2007) on art-based methods for addressing sensitive issues with children and young people. Methods included poetry, visual arts, digital art, theater, film, dance, and creative writing. They found that arts were used when verbal methods were insufficient, or individuals were too vulnerable to express issues verbally. The arts revealed invisible experiences, facilitated change and transformation, and promoted social inclusion, community building, and conflict resolution, enabling expression of taboo topics and painful experiences.

Art is a powerful tool for promoting physical and mental health. The World Health Organization (WHO) highlighted this in a scoping review of over 3000 studies (Fancourt and Finn, 2019), showing that art plays a key role in disease prevention, treatment, and overall well-being. The benefits of art are linked to its ability to foster peace and harmony, contributing to improved health which is also the root of peacebuilding activities.

These studies show that art can effectively address violence, discrimination, and intergroup conflict, and change attitudes and values. Therefore, art is a valuable tool for large-scale interventions in global conflicts and peacebuilding involving large groups or entire societies.

It can be otherwise anyway: in another study, Barongan and Hall (1995) explored how music influences perception. Twenty-seven males listened to misogynistic rap, and another twenty-seven to neutral rap. They then chose film clips to show a female participant. Of those who heard misogynistic music, 30% chose aggressive clips,

compared to 7% in the neutral condition. Those who chose violent clips believed the female participant was more uncomfortable than those who chose neutral clips.

1.5. The Ambiguity of Peacebuilding Concept: Challenges and Implications

The term "Peacebuilding" originates from the work coined by Boutros Boutros-Ghali of the United Nations in his "Agenda for Peace" (1992), as an action to identify and support structures that will tend to strengthen and consolidate peace to prevent relapse into conflict. However, it should be noted that this term has been interpreted in different ways internationally by the major world organizations, without there being agreement on its specific definition. **there is not uniform global code of PEACEBUILDING today.** Therefore, in general terms, it can be considered as a term that encompasses several sub-terms and sub-concepts, such as conflict resolution, conflict transformation, reconciliation, social cohesion, community building, and many more. Despite this lack of delimitation, this systematic review adopts the definition of "peacebuilding" provided by the UK Foreign and Commonwealth Office, which establishes this concept as an umbrella term that covers a series of activities required as a result of conflict. (Barnett, *et al*, 2007) and since it has been republished in 2021(Barnett, *et al*, 2021) it means that is still valid this coding issue.

The lack of clarity surrounding the term "peacebuilding" poses significant challenges to the effectiveness and efficiency of peace efforts. It affects practitioners, policymakers, and financiers, leading to fragmented interventions, incoherent policies, implementation difficulties, and misallocated funds. Addressing this ambiguity is crucial for enhancing the impact and sustainability of peacebuilding initiatives worldwide.

Given the challenges of international conflicts, it's clear that new tools are needed. In Afghanistan, decades of efforts for social cohesion have failed (Dodge, 2021), Israel-Palestine...don't need to reference. The war in Ukraine stems from internal conflict and has not been effectively addressed for the past twenty years (Di Rienzo, 2015). Peacebuilding success is mixed, with about 50% of aid-receiving nations re-entering conflict within five years, and 72% of peacebuilding operations leading to authoritarian regimes (Barnett et al., 2007).

1.6. Art in a decolonized peacebuilding strategy

The intersection between art and peacebuilding is an emerging interdisciplinary field that warrants deeper exploration. While art's ability to transcend language and cultural barriers and connect with human emotions is recognized, the empirical understanding of this relationship is still developing. The mechanisms through which art contributes to peacebuilding and conflict mitigation involve complex psychological, social, and cultural elements.

By unifying art and peacebuilding, a "new era" in this field can be glimpsed, fostering a more peaceful society and improving overall health and well-being, as indicated by WHO study previously mentioned. To develop a robust theoretical framework, it is crucial to study these processes systemically, understanding how art influences conflict resolution, fosters empathy, facilitates healing, and aids reconciliation.

The scoping review "Health Communication and the Arts in the United States" (Sonke et al., 2021) provides relevant insights. The arts have proven effective in promoting dialogue, increasing understanding of complex issues, and changing attitudes, beliefs, and behaviors. This potential is applicable in peacebuilding but requires further research.

UNESCO (2022) in the report "Re/Shaping Policies for Creativity. Addressing Culture as a Global Public Good" highlights the power of the arts in supporting reconciliation, rehabilitation, and reintegration. For instance, in the Central African Republic, gender-based and sexual violence in the Mole refugee camp dropped from 76% to 16% after four months of dance workshops by the Refugee on the Move program in 2016. With 70.8 million displaced people globally, including 25.9 million refugees, over half of whom are under 18, addressing underlying injustices is crucial. Artistic creativity can help restore human dignity and build peaceful societies, going beyond merely providing shelter and food.

Adaptability and cultural sensitivity are fundamental in implementing art-based peacebuilding activities. Their effectiveness depends on their relevance to the cultural experiences of target communities. This involves preliminary research and consultations to understand local needs, values, and potential barriers. Using familiar and meaningful art forms can enhance participation and engagement, respecting local cultural identities and preventing cultural colonization. Combining art-based techniques with other interventions, such as transitional justice and psychosocial support, can provide a comprehensive response to post-conflict dynamics (Naidu-Silverman, 2015).

Prioritizing local knowledge production, especially in the context of humanitarian aid, is crucial because local understanding ensures that solutions to problems are culturally relevant, considering local customs, values, and traditions, as well as resources. For instance, it would be futile to teach filmmaking to a community that has never been in contact with the complex technology required for such work, nor would it be sensible to continue subsidizing such an endeavor, because it is essential that the community can integrate any practice used so that it becomes their own. Without this relevance, interventions can be inappropriate, potentially harmful, and ineffective (Thorne, 2022).

Sustainability of interventions is enhanced when based on local knowledge and capabilities, as communities are more likely to adopt and sustain solutions they understand and value. This approach empowers communities, allowing them to actively solve their own problems, rather than being passive recipients of aid. Valuing local knowledge respects and recognizes the inherent dignity and skills of communities, making them integral to the peacebuilding process. This awareness can decolonize

humanitarian aid by challenging existing power dynamics and ensuring solutions are not imposed externally (De Coning, 2013).

Local knowledge diversity stimulates creativity and innovation, offering new ways to address problems and contribute to research. Prioritizing local knowledge ensures mutual exchange and learning, valuing both local and external expertise. This research focuses on artistic disciplines that are accessible and affordable to local populations. High-cost formats like large-scale film, television, and video games are excluded due to their material costs and tendency to create dependency on external resources, rather than emerging organically within the community.

In psychology, strategies using short fiction, films, stories, and writings are employed to modify habits as educational content. These entertainment messages can be utilized in conflict reduction, with engagement significantly influencing outcomes, as shown in a meta-analysis by Tukachinsky and Tokunaga (2013). Another emerging field involves using video games as simulations to change attitudes and promote healthy habits (Frasca, 2013).

While edutainment and video games show promise, this study excludes video games to avoid dependency on external resources and technology from economically advanced countries. This focus prevents cultural colonization and promotes sustainable, locally-driven artistic content.

Disciplines such as theater, music, dance, painting, sculpture, poetry, and storytelling can use local materials and adapt to cultural environments. Each community requires tailored approaches; for example, in Muslim societies, poetry is more accepted than photography. This research includes photography due to its accessibility and low resource needs, unlike cinema, which often creates passive subjects. It includes documentaries and modest audiovisual projects that summarize and disseminate efforts, aiding in policy adoption to improve community living conditions and support peacebuilding.

1.7. Justification of the Research

Research in this field spans various disciplines, including musicology, sociology, philosophy, ethnology, anthropology, and psychology. This review aims to evaluate initiatives and methodologies, assessing their effects on participants and communities. It will clarify how the arts can reduce intra- and intercommunity conflicts, diminish prejudices and stereotypes, reduce xenophobia, and facilitate primary mediation. Additionally, the review will examine how these interventions can complement formal mediation and diplomatic activities, using a predominantly bottom-up approach (Shank and Schirch, 2008).

Arts-based peacebuilding is a rapidly growing field, with research increasing by 400% since 2017. However, it lacks clear classifications and analysis due to its multidisciplinary nature. A reference framework defining art, involved arts, and effective methodologies is needed. Wand et al. (2017) made initial efforts to set research boundaries and identify inherent art forms. Despite these advances, art-based

processes remain under-theorized in development literature (Ware et al., 2022; Chilton & Levy, 2009).

Figure 1

SCOPUS search with Boolean arts-based AND peacebuilding between 2010-2023

Note: Made by author based on SCOPUS data, July, 2023.

Research methodologies in this field are diverse and need more consolidation and standardization. Although there are studies that have used a variety of methodological approaches, the lack of a commonly accepted methodological framework by organizations in the field makes comparison and synthesis of findings difficult. The United Nation (2010) advises in its guide the work of Lederach et al. (2007) *Reflective Peacebuilding: A Planning, Monitoring and Learning Toolkit* as accepted reference in peacebuilding, however it is mainly directed to policy makers with a top-down approach.

The interdisciplinary nature of art-based peacebuilding can pose additional challenges as researchers may have backgrounds in disciplines as diverse as fine arts, psychology, sociology, education, politics, peace and conflict studies, but this variety of theoretical and methodological approaches, while enriching the field, makes it difficult to create a coherent body of literature. This research seeks to further strengthen the union of this force which has a common goal as peacebuilding using Art-Based Peacebuilding methods.

Although ABP involves various forms of art, such as music, dance, visual arts, and theatre, the existing literature often fails to address their unique contributions. For example, how does music facilitate peacebuilding differently from theatre? While the role of art in peacebuilding is acknowledged, there is limited data on recent advancements, hindering our understanding of ABP's impact. Therefore, further research is needed to develop and validate theories and explain ABP's contributions.

Existing ABP research often prioritizes aesthetics and creativity as outcomes, but it requires a balanced analysis of both process-oriented and outcome-oriented evaluations. Skepticism towards ABP arises from perceptions of its lack of rigor compared to traditional peacebuilding approaches and its predominantly qualitative methodology. This work aims to challenge this skepticism by demonstrating that ABP can be rigorous and effective, providing greater clarity and credibility to the field (Beller, 2009).

1.8. Objectives

The premise of this work is that the arts, integral to human history, serve functions beyond enjoyment, notably in conflict transformation and peacebuilding. This systematic review aims to evaluate this premise by compiling and analyzing empirical evidence.

- The general objective is to analyze the effectiveness of art in peacebuilding worldwide through a review of scientific literature.

Specific Objectives:

- Identify and analyze research on the efficacy of arts-based interventions in peacebuilding.
- Examine different research designs and predominant methodologies in this field.
- Understand how art contributes to peacebuilding based on reviewed studies.
- Evaluate the applicability of findings in various cultural and geographic contexts with a decolonizing approach.
- Propose recommendations for future research and practices based on the literature review.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research follows the PRISMA guidelines to enhance clarity and transparency in systematic reviews and meta-analyses. The PRISMA protocol includes a 27-item checklist and a flowchart representing various stages of the review process, covering the review protocol, eligibility criteria, data extraction, synthesis methods, and presentation of results (Moher et al., 2009).

A systematic review was conducted using Scopus and Web of Science (WOS), two databases known for peer-reviewed scientific articles. The search used the keywords "arts-based" and "peacebuilding" combined with the boolean operator "AND." This search was applied to titles, abstracts, keywords, and full texts, and was conducted in English.

In May 2023, the search yielded 17 articles from WOS and 162 from Scopus, totaling 179 academic documents. This comprehensive search aimed to ensure a robust and relevant sample of literature for the review.

2.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

This study aims to advance the field of ABP through rigorous methodology and data quality. The PRISMA method guided the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the systematic review:

Disciplinary Focus: Articles were selected from psychology, social sciences, arts, and humanities to ensure relevance to ABP.

Empirical Research: Only empirical studies were included, excluding review articles, theoretical or philosophical pieces, clinical articles, and those lacking field studies. This ensures findings are based on solid, data-driven evidence.

Contextual Relevance: Studies conducted solely on campuses or schools, or those focused on social networks or theology, were excluded to allow broader generalization of findings to different context and population.

Open Access: Only open-access articles were included to promote transparency and accessibility, essential for advancing the field since it allows other researchers to access and build upon existing findings.

Specific Relevance: Articles needed to address both art-based interventions and peacebuilding. Studies mentioning only one of these aspects or using film as a research method (except documentaries) were excluded.

This approach ensures a robust, relevant, and up-to-date body of literature for evaluating ABP.

2.2 Sample Selection Procedure and Flow Diagram

Using the established inclusion and exclusion criteria, the following flow diagram illustrates the selection process (Figure 2):

Initial Sample: 179 articles from Web of Science and Scopus.

Duplicates: 11 duplicate articles removed, leaving 168 documents.

Disciplinary Focus: Application of PRISMA method, selecting articles from psychology, social sciences, and arts and humanities, reducing the sample to 103.

Open Access: Exclusion of 48 non-open-access articles.

Final Selection: Application of additional criteria, resulting in 13 studies selected for the systematic review.

Figure 2

Flow chart of the study sample selection process according to PRISMA declaration

Note. Source: own elaboration

3. RESULTS

This review focuses on thirteen studies in the emerging field of ARP. These studies explore the importance of various artistic mediums and their impact on the peace process. The selected articles examine how art serves as an instrument of change in

conflict areas worldwide, discussing different methodologies and summarizing the latest advances in the field in chronological order (Table 3).

Table 3

(a) Synthetic analysis of the selected studies.

AR AUTHORS	TITLE	DUR.	METHODOLOGY & DESIGN	ART	FACTORS & EFFECTS	REGION
Fairley, Cubillos, Muñoz.	Photography and everyday peacebuilding: Examining the impact of photographing everyday peace in Colombia	6 WEEKS	Qualitative, Systemic, Adaptive, Participatory Approach with Narrative, Discussion, and Bottom-Up Social Action, Focus Groups, Photovoice. Two Dir. Groups 45 Participants Each. Indirect 80, Others N.D.	Photography, Narrative.	Community-Level Resistance and Peacebuilding, Attitude and Perception Change, Promotion of Dialogue and Communication, Community Concrete Actions, Empowerment and Citizen Participation, Negotiation and Adaptation to Security Dynamics.	South America, Colombia
Shutt, Martin, Coetzee.	The theatre of development: dramaturgy, actors and performances in the 'workshop space'	1 MONTH	Interdisc. and Participatory Qualitative, Forum Theatre, "Hot Seating". Dir. Part.: 20 x 20 Towns, Indi. Part. N.D.	Performative Art; Theater	Although the focus has primarily been on the technique as a factor of study and its effects, it could be inferred that there is an increased awareness of gender violence and gender conflicts, and an improvement in communication skills regarding peacebuilding.	West Africa, Sierra Leone
Ware.	Metaphor in Conflict Transformations: Using Arts to Shift Perspectives and Build Empathy	3 YEARS	Longitudinal Qualitative Based on: Participant Observation, Inductive Data Analysis, Focus Groups, Session Transcripts, Field Notes, and Other Collected Artistic Materials. Direct Participants: 20, Indirect N.D.	Multidisciplinary: Drawings, Visual Metaphors, Poetry, Music	Attitude Change, Empathy Building, Commitment to Change, Memory and Application of Ideas. Effects Studied: Changes in Attitudes Toward Conflict, Empathy, and Reconciliation. Development of Greater Empathy Toward Others. Active Commitment to Changing Behaviors and Attitudes, Intra- and Intergroup Conflict Resolution, Promotion of Peaceful Participation and Community Development.	Asia, Myanmar.
Pinto-García, Serna-Hosie, Casas, Méndez.	Art for Reconstruction: A creative and art-based intervention for peacebuilding and reconciliation to reduce intergroup hostility and stigma after a protracted armed conflict.	7 MONTHS	Mixed Method, Qualitative and Quantitative. Surveys Pre- and Post-Public Exhibitions, Longitudinal Participant Interviews, Activity Observations and Records. Inductive Qualitative Coding: 54 Participants in 2 Groups. Indirect Participants Measured 51 (out of 600).	Multidisciplinary: Kintsugi, Drawing, Clay, and Collage, with Adjunctive Yoga, Feldenkrais, Mindfulness.	Factors: Conflict and Trauma Experiences, Healing and Reconciliation, Empathy and Understanding, Audience Reactions (Stigma and Conflict Resolution Perception). Effects: Increased Awareness and Self-Knowledge, Improved Communication and Conflict Resolution Skills, Greater Empathy and Understanding, Reduced Prejudice and Stereotypes, Enhanced Empathy and Compassion.	South America, Colombia
Bliesemann de Guevara, Refale, Furnari, Gamero, Julian, Payson.	Drawing Out Experiential Conflict Knowledge in Myanmar: Arts-Based Methods in Qualitative Research With Conflict-Affected Communities	3 DAYS	Qualitative, DrawingOut Method, Group Discussions, and Informal Interviews. Direct Participants: 11.	Multidisciplinary: Visual and Literary Art, Metaphorical Drawings	Factors: Experience of Violence, Perceptions of Peace, Development Perspectives. Effects: Improved Understanding of Conflict, Strengthened Local Ownership of the Peace Process, Enhanced Inclusion & Equality, Increased Trust and Communication Among NP (Nonviolent Peaceforce) Partners from Different Geographical and Ethnic Regions.	Asia, Myanmar.
Breed, Pells, Elliott, Prentki.	Mobile Arts for Peace (MAP): creating art-based communication structures between young people and policy-makers from local to national levels	4 YEARS	Qualitative, Participatory, Collaborative, and Longitudinal Approach (2017-2021), Collection of Stories and Experiences. Participants N.D.	Multidisciplinary: Music, Theater, Documentary, Visual Arts, and Dance.	Conflict Transformation, Building Shared Identities, Justice & Reconciliation, Dialogue & Mutual Understanding, Attitude & Perception Change, Social Awareness, Youth Empowerment.	Africa, Ruanda.

Note: This table contains the fundamental data of the first 6 investigations out of a total of 13 such as: authors, title, duration, methodology and design, participants, type of art involved, factors and effects studied, continent and country.

Table 3

(b) Synthetic analysis of the selected studies.

YEAR	AUTHORS	TITLE	DUR.	METHODOLOGY & DESIGN	ART	FACTORS & EFFECTS	REGION
7	2022	Hirschmann, Van Doetsum, Playing with the enemy: Investigating the impact of musical peacebuilding.	EVERY SUMMER, 20 YEARS	Qualitative, Two Studies with Narratives and Interviews. Total of 86 Participants.	Performative Art: Music	Fact.: Motivation for Participation, Change Perception & Trust, Listening Skills. Effects: Mosts joined for musical, not political, motive, increased intimacy, especially in informal & spontaneous rehearsals, increased closeness between parties. Some became active peace facilitators in their personal environments. Changes in mutual perceptions and trust were noted, especially with repeated participation.	Europe and the Middle East: Serbia, Bosnia, Kosovo, and Croatia, Israel, Palestine, and Arab Countries.
8	2021	Lara-Guerrero, Responding to violence from abroad: The Mexican diaspora mobilising from Brussels and Paris through art-based strategies	2014 - 2018	Exploratory: Qualitative, Semi-Structured Interviews (41), Participant Observations (55 Events)	Multidisciplinary: Music, Theater, Visual and Performative Art, Documentary.	Factors: Artists' Strategies, Audience Emotional and Cognitive Response, Transnational Political Involvement of Migrants, Impact on Peacebuilding. Effects: Awareness of Violence in Mexico, Humanization of Victims, Political Involvement of Migrants, Contribution to Peacebuilding, Mobilization and Support.	Europe: Bruxelles, Paris
9	2021	Floresta, Undoing a culture of violence in schools by hearing the subalterned students who experience war in Mindanao	2017	Phenomenological, Interviews, Focus Groups. 56 Participants including Current and Former Students Aged 15 to 53 Years.	Multidisciplinary: Visual Arts, Literary Arts; Drawing, Visual Works, Narrative.	Building and Reinforcing a Positive Identity, Establishing Non-Violent Environments, Using Students' Religious Identity to Promote a Non-Violent Culture, Fostering Religious Sensitivity, and Addressing the Effects of Violence and Grievances.	Asia: Philippines, Mindanao Region.
10	2021	Dimstorfer, Saud A Stage for the Unknown? Reconciling Postwar Communities through Theatre-Facilitated		Qualitative, Narrative Reports, Long-Term Observations. Participants: 48 Facilitators, 6 Theater Teams, 292 Events, 16,000 Direct Participants on One Occasion.	Multidisciplinary, Performative Art and Visual Arts; Theater, Storytelling, Final Documentary.	The Power of Stories and Memories, Dialogue and Imagination, Empathy and Mutual Understanding, The Relationship Between Past, Present, and Future, Changes in Perceptions and Attitudes Over Time. Effects: Revelation of Hidden Stories, Fostering Imagination of a Peaceful Future, Development of Empathy and Mutual Understanding, Transformation of Perceptions and Attitudes, Facilitation of Non-Cognitive Communication, Increased Engagement of Political Leaders.	Asia, Nepal, 6 districts.
11	2020	Ubaldo, Hinqen S., Rwandan music-makers negotiate shared cultural identities after genocide: the case of Orchestre Impérial's revival	2014 - 2015	Qualitative and Ethnographic. Semi-Structured Interviews, Informal Interviews, Letters, Participant Observation.	Performative Art: Music, Musicking	Factors: Cultural and Musical Identity, Reconciliation and Overcoming Ethnic Divisions, Commemoration of Genocide Victims, Promotion of Peace and Unity. Effects: Building Collective Identity, Promoting Reconciliation, Emotional Healing, Fostering Social Cohesion.	Africa, Ruanda.
12	2019	Mutero, Kaye, Music and Conflict Transformation in Zimbabwe	3 YEARS	Qualitative, Interviews, Focus Groups, Participant Observation, Participatory Action Research, Direct Participants: 15 from 2 Ethnic Groups, Male and Female. Indirect N.D.	Performative Art: Music, Dance, and Image Theater	Factors: Cultural and Ethnic, Interpersonal and Group, Community Impact. Effects: Transformation of Internal Conflict, Development of Interpersonal and Group Skills, Promotion of Cultural Identity and Unity, Community Impact, Resilience Against Oppression.	Africa, Zimbabwe
13	2019	Scranom, McLaughlin, Heroes on the Hill: A qualitative study of the psychosocial benefits of an intercultural arts programme for youth in Northern Ireland	ND	Mixed Qualitative and Quantitative, Semi-Structured Interviews Before and After, Direct Participants: 10+2, Indirect Participants: 70-700.	Performative Art: Music and Dance	Factors: Prevalence of Bullying, Development of Resilience, Intercommunity Relations. Effects: Improvement in Self-Confidence and Sense of Achievement, Intercommunity Cohesion, Development of Intercultural Awareness and Cultural Pride.	Europe, Ireland

Note: This table contains the fundamental data of the last 7 investigations out of a total of 13 such as: authors, title, duration, methodology and design, participants, type of art involved, factors and effects studied, continent and country.

"Photography and Everyday Peacebuilding: Examining the Impact of Photographing Everyday Peace in Colombia" (Fairey et al., 2023) explores the use of the photovoice method in post-conflict communities of Urama and Las Cruces, Colombia. These communities, which had not received state post-conflict funding, faced security challenges due to the presence of armed actors. The photovoice project aimed to highlight the inequality in state support between peasants and ex-combatants and documented the lack of basic services. Photovoice, a participatory research methodology combining photography, narrative, and community empowerment, was employed with forty-five participants primarily women. The project produced 44 Indicators Photographic Stories, 41 individual projects, and 3 collective projects, involving an additional 80 community members in discussions and reflections on local issues. The methodology, developed by Wang and Burris (1997), focused on using photography and group dialogue to address and reflect on local problems, fostering critical dialogue, promoting social action and is grounded in feminist theories. The study observed that photovoice facilitated dialogue, strengthened community resilience, and fostered a sense of identity and commitment to peace. However, it also highlighted the limitations and tensions of using cameras in conflict settings, suggesting the need for cautious and adaptive practices. The research indicates that photovoice is a valuable tool for peacebuilding, enabling safe and effective community engagement. Future research should investigate the gender dimensions, longevity of impacts, and explore other art forms in peacebuilding to address the inherent tensions in using cameras in conflict environments.

"The Theatre of Development: Dramaturgy, Actors, and Performances in the 'Workshop Space'" (Shutt et al., 2023) examines the use of theatre as a tool for conflict resolution and peacebuilding. The authors analyze a theatre workshop in a rural Sierra Leone community focused on gender-based violence. Using dramaturgical analysis, they employed techniques such as forum theatre and "hot-seating," where audience members interact with characters to explore scene details and encourage active participation and reflection. Forum theatre presented unresolved crises for the audience to explore multiple solutions. The study found these techniques helped participants challenge gender norms and power relations but noted that existing community dynamics influenced participation and discussion. Preparation involved NGO workers, three actors, and two researchers, with 40 community participants, including 25 women. The authors conclude that theatre can be an effective peacebuilding tool, but it is crucial to consider and address community power dynamics. They recommend future efforts focus on challenging and changing these dynamics in Sierra Leonean communities.

"Metaphor in Conflict Transformation: Using Arts to Shift Perspectives and Build Empathy" (Ware, 2022) investigates how art-based metaphors contribute to conflict transformation and reconciliation in communities affected by ethnic tensions. It examines how these metaphors help participants reflect on and change their attitudes and behaviors related to conflict. Using a longitudinal qualitative approach, the study employed art workshops as the primary means of facilitating reflection and transformation. Activities included creating visual metaphors, storytelling, and

theatrical performances, allowing participants to express their emotions and perspectives on conflict. Over three years, 20 villages selected Rakhine (Buddhist) facilitators who attended training sessions every 6-8 weeks and participated in biannual 2-3 day art-based peacebuilding workshops. Facilitators were two-thirds men and one-third women, aged 18-65, although there is no data on broader community participation and outcomes. Workshops aimed to include diverse ethnic and religious groups but were conducted intragroup with the Rakhine community due to external factors. Art-based metaphors in these workshops had significant effects, enabling participants to explore new perspectives, challenge stereotypes, and develop empathy. Reports indicated shifts in attitudes and behaviors, with participants engaging in conflict resolution, reconciliation, and active peacebuilding. The study suggests future research should explore resistance to change in intercommunity conflicts, compare metaphors in different settings, and evaluate the long-term impact of workshops on conflict transformation and sustained positive changes in attitudes and behaviors.

"Art for Reconstruction: A Creative and Art-Based Intervention for Peacebuilding and Reconciliation" (Pinto-Garcia et al., 2022) aimed to promote reconciliation and heal trauma in Medellín, Colombia, through creative and artistic interventions. It employed multidisciplinary techniques including Kintsugi, nonviolent communication, yoga, mindfulness, and Feldenkrais over three stages spanning seven months. The first stage focused on healing trauma and individual reconciliation through counseling sessions that included drawing, clay work, collage, mindfulness, yoga, and Feldenkrais. The second stage targeted interpersonal reconciliation using nonviolent communication, role-play, and Kintsugi. The third stage involved a mobile museum with an art exhibition, recording visitor attendance (86 out of 600), before and after the event. The intervention included 54 participants, consisting of civilian survivors, retired military and police veterans, and individuals in the Reintegration Process who were former combatants from guerrillas and paramilitary groups. All participants were affected by the armed conflict. A mixed-methods design assessed changes in participants' perceptions and behaviors, utilizing both qualitative and quantitative data, which showed positive effects despite the small sample size. The Kintsugi technique, symbolizing the beauty of imperfection and resilience, helped participants reinterpret their memories and experiences. The study examined changes in perceptions and emotions towards ex-combatants and victims, as well as the willingness to collaborate on pro-social goals. Positive changes were observed in emotion control, perception of others, and empathy towards ex-combatants. The project demonstrated that creative and artistic interventions could effectively process trauma and promote reconciliation. Although the findings have limitations in generalization, the study highlighted the potential of combining different disciplines within the context of transitional justice and reconciliation. Future research should increase the number of observations and evaluate the long-term effects of the program.

"Drawing-Out Experiential Conflict Knowledge in Myanmar: Arts-Based Methods in Qualitative Research With Conflict-Affected Communities" (Bliesemann de Guevara et al., 2022) explores the use of art-based methods for conflict resolution. It

describes a project in Myanmar using drawings to explore the experiences of violence-affected communities in Kachin. Designed as qualitative research, the study involved 11 local adults in a 3-day workshop. The DrawingOut method enabled participants to express their experiences related to violence, peace, and development. Findings indicated that drawing facilitated a deeper understanding of the complexities of local violence and enhanced community participation in the research. The authors conclude that art-based methods are valuable for conflict resolution as they access deep contextual knowledge and strengthen local actor involvement in peacebuilding and development. The study emphasizes the importance of incorporating local voices in peacebuilding research, contrasting traditional methods that often overlook the experiences of those affected by conflict. It highlights the need for adequate training for researchers using these methods and the importance of establishing strong partnerships with local actors to ensure the relevance and sustainability of art-based interventions.

"Mobile Arts for Peace (MAP): Creating Art-Based Communication Structures Between Young People and Policy-Makers" (Breed et al., 2022) describes the MAP project in Rwanda, which uses applied arts to engage young people in policy formulation and social change. The project addresses challenges such as limited educational and employment opportunities, disenchantment with formal political processes, and barriers to civic participation. MAP adopts a bottom-up approach, involving young people as primary participants, expressing their experiences through art. MAP collaborates with civil society organizations, cultural organizations, schools, government agencies, and local authorities. Activities include mapping art-based initiatives, training young educators, and creating art-based materials. Through performances and dialogue, MAP explores topics like disability, discrimination, child abuse, and teenage pregnancy, aiming to inform policies by creating dialogue spaces between young people and political actors. Art-based methods, policy reports, and performances facilitate discussions and develop recommendations, challenging traditional power dynamics and empowering young people in decision-making processes. The project promotes personal autonomy, democratic participation, and the transformation of personal experiences into social change. Despite the complexities and unpredictability of art-based policy formulation, MAP's successes in Rwanda have led to increased funding and ongoing initiatives. The project has developed professional development programs in collaboration with educational and medical institutions to incorporate art-based approaches and mental health support. Based on Article 13 of the Convention on the Rights of the Child (UNICEF, 2006), MAP allows participants to choose their medium of expression, such as music, dance, theater, visual arts, and film. Through interviews, discussion groups, and surveys, young participants share their stories and ideas, informing policy design and guiding advocacy actions. The authors recommend maintaining participatory approaches, ensuring young people are integral to decision-making and implementation. They emphasize seeking long-term sustainability through strategic alliances, continuous funding, evaluating and adjusting

strategies, strengthening alliances, promoting research, and adapting to contextual changes to maintain relevance and effectiveness.

"Playing with the Enemy: Investigating the Impact of Musical Peacebuilding" (Hirschmann and Van Doesum, 2022) explores the role of music in conflict resolution and intercultural understanding. It analyzes two cases: the Colluvio Chamber Music Academy (TCCMA) and the West-Eastern Divan Orchestra (WEDO). In the TCCMA study, qualitative research methods, including interviews and direct observations, were used with 11 participants from Kosovo, Serbia, Bosnia, and Croatia. In the WEDO study, narratives of 22 musicians from Israel, Palestine, and other countries were analyzed. Founded by Daniel Barenboim and Edward Said, WEDO brings together young musicians from conflict-ridden regions. Both studies examined musicians' motivations to join the programs, the mechanism of listening, and changes in mutual perceptions and trust. The findings revealed that participants primarily joined for musical rather than political reasons. Close listening and interaction increased during informal rehearsals, leading to positive changes in mutual perceptions and trust. Some musicians even became active peace facilitators in their communities. The results suggest that well-organized musical initiatives provide an effective medium for peacebuilding. Musicians improved their listening skills and mutual understanding, experiencing changes in perceptions and trust towards members of other groups. Informal and spontaneous activities were found to be particularly effective in fostering attentive listening and mutual understanding. Repeated participation was key in building trust and a sense of common identity, with WEDO maintaining its summer project annually since 1999. This continuity has contributed to sustained and improved changes among participants.

"Responding to Violence from Abroad: The Mexican Diaspora Mobilizing from Brussels and Paris through Art-Based Strategies" (Lara-Guerrero, 2021) explores how Mexican migrant artists in Europe use art to raise awareness about violence in Mexico and foster resilience and capacity building. The research, conducted in Brussels and Paris in 2017 and 2023, involved interviews with Mexican activists and observations of artistic and cultural events, focusing on theater, music, and art exhibitions. The effect of these art forms was studied through attendance at 55 events as a participant observer. Data was collected from both direct participants, such as artists and organizers, and indirect participants, including the general public. Fieldwork included interviews with 41 Mexican political activists. The study employed interpretive research methods, viewing humans as active agents. In Brussels, a play depicted Mexico's history of violence, and a music concert paid tribute to victims. In Paris, an art installation presented 40 pairs of shoes representing victims, with messages carved into the floor. These activities engaged both direct participants (artists and organizers) and indirect participants (the general public). The findings indicate that these art-based strategies effectively raised awareness about violence and impunity in Mexico, questioning the capacity of Mexican institutions to provide security and justice. The strategies also helped Mexican migrants educate others and build capacity around the conflict in Europe. Furthermore, they contributed to overcoming the psychological

trauma of violence. The study concludes that Mexican migrants in Europe have played a significant role in transforming the conflict in Mexico and building awareness to improve security. For future research, it suggests exploring how transnational political practices of migrants can contribute to conflict resolution and political reconstruction in their home countries.

"Undoing a culture of violence in schools by hearing the subalterned students who experience war in Mindanao" (Floresta, 2021) examines a project-based work in the context of Mindanao, Philippines, and how art can be used as a means to address and overcome conflicts. The research is based on a phenomenological methodology and in-depth interviews and group discussions were conducted with two groups of participants: current students (CS) and former students (FS). A total of 54 participants were recruited from a Muslim religious minority. There were 36 current students and 18 former students who participated in the study, aged between 15 and 53 years old. As an inclusion criteria, all participants had to have experienced conflicts during school time, and former students, in addition, had to have current roles in the community. The study explored various art forms, including drawing, visual works, and narratives, as part of group discussions and individual expressions. These activities provided a medium for participants to express their experiences and emotions related to violence, exploring alternative ways to handle conflicts. The study examined the construction of positive identities through art, the establishment of non-violent environments in violent communities, the use of religious identity to promote non-violence, the development of religious sensitivity, and understanding and addressing the effects of violence. The study concluded that youth empowerment, creating non-violent school environments, and including religious identity in peacebuilding programs are crucial. The author recommends promoting active student participation in planning and executing peacebuilding programs and strengthening cultural and religious sensitivity in conflict-affected communities.

"A Stage for the Unknown? Reconciling Postwar Communities through Theatre-Facilitated" (Dirnstorfer and Saud, 2021) details an initiative in Nepal that uses theater as a means to facilitate dialogue and promote reconciliation in communities affected by armed conflict. The strategy, called "EnActing Dialogue", employed Playback Theatre, an interactive form where experiences/stories shared by the audience are dramatized by the actors. The active participation of local leaders and the versatility of dialogue facilitators contributed to the program's success. The performances evolved from conflict-related stories to contemporary and personal challenges. While the research design is not specified, it is inferred to be a qualitative case study based on longitudinal observations and analyses. The program reached over 16,000 audience members and involved 48 dialogue facilitators in 6 theater companies, including male and female ex-combatants, with 50 percent women and a balanced representation of castes and ethnic groups. The facilitators organized 292 performances in coordination with local advisors in communities with many ex-combatants and conflict victims. Six diverse communities from Nepal participated continuously over three years. Documentary material from the theatrical events and printed documentation of selected stories communicated experiences to politicians and rulers.

This artistic approach awakens memories and emotions, providing a safe space for self-expression and social transformation, akin to a therapeutic environment. The study examined community participation, inclusivity, diversity, and the evolution of themes in the theatrical representations. Results indicate that this form of theatre contributed to reconciliation, mutual recognition, and the breakdown of stereotypes and prejudices. It supported the transformation of individual and collective identities and significantly aided the reconciliation process in conflict-affected societies. The initiative accessed hidden memories and experiences, fostering the imagination of a peaceful future. The study suggests that reconciliation initiatives should include artistic forms and provide spaces for self-reflection for artists and facilitators. It also emphasizes the importance of adapting to evolving performance themes from conflict-related stories to contemporary personal issues.

"Rwandan music-makers negotiate shared cultural identities after genocide: the case of Orchestre Impala's revival" (Ubaldo, Hintjens, 2020) explores the impact of music on peacebuilding and conflict resolution in Rwanda post-1994 genocide. Focusing on Orchestre Impala, a band active since the 1970s, the research employs qualitative and ethnographic methods, including interviews with band members and analysis of their lyrics and musical style. Orchestre Impala, known for blending traditional Rwandan music with Congolese rumba, has played a significant role in national reconciliation and promoting unity by using music to celebrate everyday life, convey political messages, and commemorate genocide victims. The study underscores music's potential in reconstructing cultural identity and bridging ethnic divides in Rwandan society, while cautioning against its politicization and stressing the need for balancing artistic expression with peace and reconciliation goals. The authors suggest that similar approaches in other art forms could further enhance peacebuilding efforts.

"Music and Conflict Transformation in Zimbabwe" (Mutero, Kaye, 2019) examines the role of music and art in conflict resolution and peacebuilding in Zimbabwe. Over three years, the author led the creation of a musical ensemble with members from the Shona and Ndebele ethnic groups to address ethnic tensions. The ensemble, comprising fifteen men and women from diverse religious, ethnic, and political backgrounds, aimed to educate, socialize, and foster entrepreneurship. Using an assets-based community development approach, the study leveraged community skills and knowledge to restore peace. It adopted participatory action research, including 44 group discussions, ethnographic interviews, and musical creation. Participants experienced and resolved tensions and disagreements through dialogue, music, dance, and image theater. Music played a crucial role in providing an emotional outlet and uniting group members. The study found that music and art helped establish shared values based on Ubuntu ("I am because we are") and enhanced unity, participation, and decision-making. Concerts reflected the ensemble's social cohesion, impacting the broader community. The study concluded that music and art are powerful tools for conflict resolution and peacebuilding, allowing expression beyond spoken language. The author recommends more team-building activities and adapting these methods to other contexts and ethnic groups.

"Heroes on the Hill: A Qualitative Study of the Psychosocial Benefits of an Intercultural Arts Program for Youth in Northern Ireland" (Scrantom and McLaughlin, 2019) addresses bullying in Northern Ireland and the role of the Heroes on the Hill program in promoting resilience and intercommunity relationships. The initiative aimed to improve community relations, celebrate diversity, increase social inclusion, and boost arts participation. A qualitative and quantitative analysis was conducted with 12 participants (10 girls and 2 boys, average age 12) who engaged in dance and playwriting sessions. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and analyzed alongside the participation of approximately 70 youth in final performances and the attendance of about 700 community members. The program's activities, incorporating elements from various cultural traditions, aimed to enhance self-expression and explore identity and community themes. Key factors studied included bullying prevalence, resilience development, and intercommunity friendship formation. Participants experienced increased self-confidence and resilience. However, the program did not definitively reduce bullying or improve community relations overall. The program successfully promoted diversity, increased arts participation, and enhanced social inclusion. Future research should consider a longitudinal study to understand the longevity of intercommunity relationships and the role of social networks in maintaining these connections, as well as to measure the program's broader community impact.

3.1. Results Analysis

The analysis of the selected studies reveals that those artistic methods, such as photography, theatre, music, and visual art, effectively express emotions, experiences, and perspectives in peacebuilding contexts. These forms of artistic expression allow participants to communicate issues that might be harder to convey through formal dialogue. Art provides a symbolic and abstract language that transcends verbal limitations, enabling individuals to express their experiences and feelings in different art forms. Studies by Mutero and Kaye (2019) and Scrantom and McLaughlin (2019) demonstrate that music, theatre, and dance are effective for conflict resolution and peacebuilding in Zimbabwe and Northern Ireland. The effectiveness of these arts varies by context and mechanism, highlighting the diverse potential of artistic methods in fostering peace and understanding.

In the Mutero and Kaye (2019) study, music emerged as a vital means to alleviate ethnic tensions and promote unity within the group in Zimbabwe, integrating dance and image theatre, providing an additional channel for participants to express their emotions and experiences. In this case, the impact mechanism appeared to be the ability of music and art to transcend language barriers and ethnic differences, expressing meanings by a unified group identity and their "body" impact to the audience with significant potential for systemic change on a deeper level. Therefore, although the choice of art form may largely be dictated by the specific cultural context and the intervention's objectives, the underlying mechanisms seem to lie in art's ability to

facilitate expression, provide a safe space to explore delicate topics, and promote inclusion and diversity.

Conflicts and post-conflict situations are filled with tensions, traumas, and complex experiences that are hard to address rationally. The arts provide a safe, creative space for people to explore and share their experiences symbolically and meaningfully. Artistic activities have the power to generate empathy in those who engage with artistic works and in the audience that resonate with the vibrant artistic experiences and perspectives, leading to greater mutual understanding and bridge-building among communities divided by conflicts transcending cultural, linguistic, and social barriers.

Among the results highlighted by most studies is that art can be an effective tool for increasing community involvement in peacebuilding, changing attitudes, perceptions, and increasing social cohesion. Another important finding is the empowerment of communication and interpersonal skills through dialogue, especially in regions affected by conflicts such as Colombia, Sierra Leone, northern Myanmar, Rwanda, Nepal, and Zimbabwe. Participation in artistic activities on peacebuilding helped reconciliation and conflict transformation in communities, transformation of ethnic tensions, facilitation of discussion and understanding of sensitive issues, such as gender violence, reducing prejudices and stereotypes.

In some cases, participation in artistic activities helped to raise awareness about political issues and mobilize people for action.

Although some studies claim to achieve desired effects, they often lack follow-up to determine if changes are lasting. There is insufficient analysis of indirect participants and the broader community, with exceptions being Dirnstorfer and Saud (2021), Scrantom and McLaughlin (2019), and Ware (2022). Most studies lack a systemic approach, except for Fairey et al. (2023), Dirnstorfer and Saud (2021), and Shutt et al. (2023), which include broader community context and analyze the effects of conflict dynamics and resolutions. For changes to be effective, local social powers and status must be considered.

The predominance of qualitative methodologies in this field is notable, except for one phenomenological approach. These methodologies delve deeply into participants' experiences, perceptions, and contextual realities, often employing participatory and collaborative approaches to incorporate participants' voices. Primary data collection techniques include focus groups, semi-structured and informal interviews, and participant observation. Personal narratives are also frequently used. Only two studies employ mixed-methods approaches, blending qualitative and quantitative methods to explore participants' experiences and collect community-specific statistics. Participant groups vary significantly in size, often involving small numbers, aligning with the qualitative focus on depth over breadth. These studies emphasize conflict resolution through art-based interventions, highlighting the value of qualitative methods in understanding complex environments and individual experiences.

Studies demonstrate that practices based on art and culture can serve as a common language that transcends ethnic, racial, and religious differences helping foster social cohesion and unity by creating a sense of shared identity and purpose. These findings highlight the importance of art-based activities as effective tools for reconciliation in communities affected by conflict. Each community and conflict are unique, and effective approach in one context may not necessarily be so in another. Each intervention must be relative and adapted to the context in which it is developed, analyzing in detail its needs and resources, whether artistic or in the form of resolving traditional conflicts, to focus projects in a way that they integrate into its culture and thus allow the results to be long-lasting also because the forms of art used can be developed and disseminated directly by them, without the need for external resources. It is noted that projects developed over a long period of time tend to have permanent results.

While not a specific focus of this study, several studies also highlight attention to gender issues as part of their approaches.

4. CONCLUSION

The duration of interventions allows for a deeper and more lasting transformation of concepts, feelings, and beliefs, leading to irreversible changes in integrating others' differences in attitudes and behaviors. This approach is more effective than short-term reflections, which might not significantly impact broader community change. This concept is particularly relevant in peacebuilding, as noted in the difference between studies that have incorporated long-term approaches and those that have not. The longitudinal nature of studies is fundamental for sustaining the process within both direct and indirect groups in the community over time.

Conflict and peace are dynamic phenomena influenced by factors at various levels: subjective, group, community, national, and international. Different art disciplines offer unique perspectives on peacebuilding, making multidisciplinary approaches more effective. Addressing intergroup conflict starts with recognizing perceived differences and incompatibilities but conflict transformation focuses on finding "common ground" and similarities, which is part of the long-term reconciliation process which works on slowly integrating differences. This process requires forming peaceful relationships based on trust, cooperation, and mutual needs, culminating in mutual acceptance. Psychological aspects of reconciliation involve changing conflict behaviors and addressing the social beliefs, goals, and concerns of the groups (Bar-Tal, 2000).

There is a minimal presence of quantitative studies in this field, which could allow for a detailed understanding of patterns and general trends, even a lack of transformation of qualitative approaches into quantitative ones for general data. This is inherent in the previous point where a minimal presence of audience measurement is mentioned, then little consideration of the importance of this factor.

The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child recognizes young people's right to actively participate in peacebuilding. Globally, many young people challenge elders to address conflict root causes and seek peaceful resolutions by urging adults to act for peace and setting examples with their actions. While better inclusion in formal peace processes is needed, it's also important to acknowledge their current engagement in peacebuilding and the urgency of including them more (Pruitt, 2011).

4.1. Improvements for the future

Adopt a Long-term Perspective

Future works should view peacebuilding through art as an ongoing, dynamic process. Instead of focusing solely on immediate outcomes, studies should track the enduring effects and evolution of these interventions within communities. This longitudinal approach will capture the subtle yet significant changes that can profoundly influence societal and cultural dynamics.

Implement Systematic Approaches

Researchers should incorporate a variety of factors into their evaluations of art-based peacebuilding programs. This includes actively engaging the community, facilitating meaningful dialogue and reconciliation, and thoroughly analyzing the power dynamics at play. Systematic approach will allow for a more comprehensive assessment of the interventions' effectiveness and their ripple effects on the community.

Strengthen Community Involvement

Encourage greater community participation and involvement in both the design and implementation of art-based interventions. This inclusion helps ensure that the programs are culturally relevant and more deeply embedded in the social fabric, enhancing their sustainability and impact.

Unification of Art-Based Peacebuilding concept

To conduct this study, an initial comprehensive search combined terms related to art and peacebuilding. Key peacebuilding concepts such as conflict transformation and resolution, reconciliation, social cohesion, and community building were explored alongside artistic terms like poetry, music, dance, painting, visual arts, theater, performing art, storytelling and photography.

Currently, there's a noticeable gap in integrating these concepts, although Barone and Eisner (1997) proposed "art-based research" as a unifying term. In this context, "art-based peacebuilding" would be a more appropriate unified term to streamline research and enhance communication across these fields. This unification is not only theoretical but also practical; for instance, a SCOPUS database search using "art-based AND peacebuilding" identified 162 studies, but broadening the scope to include related

subcategories could potentially increase this to 45,296 studies, demonstrating the vast potential for a unified approach (Table 4).

Table 4

Search in SCOPUS for Various Terms Related to Art and Peacebuilding.

TERMS IN SCOPUS "ALL FIELDS"		PEACEBUILDING	PEACEBUILDING					
			CONFLICT TRASFORMATION	CONFLICT RESOLUTION	RECONCILIATION	SOCIAL COHESION	COMMUNITY BUILDING	total
ART-BASED		162	106	199	378	130	195	1008
ART-BASED	POETRY	147	147	810	3230	366	316	5016
	MUSIC	428	428	2270	4458	1397	1051	10032
	DANCE	238	238	1870	2571	813	606	6336
	PAINTING	74	74	467	1691	245	187	2738
	VISUAL ART	54	54	243	681	158	181	1371
	PERFORMING ART	47	47	168	300	134	107	803
	THEATRE	381	381	2110	4037	749	736	8394
	STORYTELLING	320	320	1402	2663	541	948	6194
	PHOTOGRAPHY	90	90	529	1771	365	453	3298
	total	1779	1885	10068	21780	4898	4780	45190

Note: The table shows how many studies would be found if these two comprehensive terms were used for each category. Source: author's own elaboration, July 2023.

This observation underscores the significance of integrating the concepts of art and peacebuilding within the research arena. By developing a general and coherent framework, enhanced communication, research, and understanding of artistic initiatives directed towards peacebuilding could be facilitated. Furthermore, this approach would create new opportunities for knowledge exchange and progress in this continually developing field.

Performing comprehensive review of Arts-based Peacebuilding

To enhance understanding of ABP, we propose conducting a comprehensive review of the 45,190 studies previously identified with a mixed-method approach with both qualitative and quantitative analysis that will allow to synthesize findings, identify trends, and analyze methodological approaches across these studies, providing a broader insight than has never been done.

The findings will enrich the evidence base in the field of art-based peacebuilding (ARP), informing the design of artistic interventions and supporting evidence-based policies and practices. This review will offer valuable insights into the impact of art on peace processes, potentially a watershed moment as a new era for practical applications in peacebuilding for governments, institutions, and organizations worldwide.

Inclusive Classification of Art Forms for Research

There is currently no comprehensive classification of all art forms for research purposes, a task complicated by the continuous evolution and creation of new styles. Future research would benefit from an inclusive framework that accommodates both existing and emerging art forms, serving as a flexible reference point that can integrate new artistic developments.

Enhancing Methodology with Participant Observation

While participant observation offers valuable insights in qualitative research, adding a non-participant researcher during data collection can enhance the methodology. This researcher can analyze and interview the participant observers, offering an additional perspective that helps mitigate the limitations of participant observation and improve data validity and reliability. Ideally, this researcher would be involved in all research stages, from study design to result interpretation.

Integrating Artistic Techniques with Traditional Peacebuilding Approaches

A key advancement in peacebuilding would be the integration of artistic techniques with traditional systems to create comprehensive programs that leverage both approaches. By establishing dialogue and collaboration between artists and peace professionals, creative skills can be combined with conflict resolution expertise to develop strategies grounded in solid conceptual frameworks. Programs could incorporate traditional peacebuilding elements like mediation and reconciliation, using structured facilitation to enhance communication and resolve conflicts through art. Additionally, partnering with local communities and institutions ensures that artistic outputs align with traditional justice and governance systems, influencing decision-making and policy implementation related to peace and conflict resolution.

This integration necessitates ongoing collaboration between artists, peace professionals, and communities, blending diverse skills and insights to enhance the effectiveness of peacebuilding initiatives.

4.2. Limitations of this research

Absence of an Interdisciplinary Team: This research lacks diverse perspectives and a multidimensional analysis due to not having an interdisciplinary team, which may limit a comprehensive understanding and representation of the topic.

Restricted Access to Studies: An inability to access 50 studies due to lack of agreements between the university and journals, and their unavailability to the public, restricts the data available, impacting the depth and validity of the findings.

Methodological Analysis Constraints: The study could not deeply analyze the methodology used in the field, including whether to employ Lederach's toolkit, Galtung's Transcend Method, or newer approaches like somatic psychology, which could be more suitable given advances in neuroscience.

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